

Functional Materials for Environmental Remediation

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Fenton catalysts ($\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{Fe}^{2+}$) are employed for environmental remediation through the Fenton mechanism involving reactive oxygen species (ROS). Storage and transportation of H_2O_2 limits its applications. ROS mediated oxidation process involved in Fenton process and semi-conductor based photo catalysis, is attributed for dye degradation and antimicrobial applications in waste water. Usually in latter process, semiconductor photocatalysts such as TiO_2 and ZnO are being used, as these generate ROS through redox reactions of holes and electrons generated in aqueous suspensions due to absorption of light. However, there is a need for development of a catalyst that generates ROS even in absence of light so that the applications are enhanced.

In this talk, our successful efforts in the design and development of such a new catalyst, $\text{ZnO}_2/\text{Polypyrrole}$, that generates ROS even in absence of light through synergy and its application in dye degradation will be illustrated [1]. It is to be noted that neither ZnO_2 nor Polypyrrole degrades dyes in presence or absence of visible light. Furthermore, the rate of dye degradation of our nanocomposite is higher than that of the commercial catalyst.

We have also linked photocatalytic reaction to Fenton reaction in the catalyst $\text{ZnO}_2/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ that could have potential applications, as it employs solid oxidant ZnO_2 in place of less stable H_2O_2 [2].

References

1. V. Lakshmi Prasanna, R. Vijayaraghavan, A new synergetic nanocomposite for dye degradation in dark and light (2016) *Scientific Reports*, 6; 38606 -11.
2. V. Lakshmi Prasanna, R. Vijayaraghavan, Simultaneous Fenton – Photocatalytic Reactions in a New Single Catalyst (nano $\text{ZnO}_2 / \text{Fe}^{2+}$) for dye degradation (2017) *Journal of Physical Chemistry*, 121 (34), 18557–18563.